

SPEECH ERRORS IN SPEECH ACTIVITY

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Annotation: This article is about classification of speech errors, examples of speech errors. And addition, Scholars have different opinions about the speech and speech errors. Speech is important component and concept of the culture.

Key words: slips of the tongue, mechanisms, perseverations, spoonersims, Malapropisms.

We consider speech to be an abstract category that does not exist for direct perception. At the same time, it is the most important indicator of human culture, his intellect and thinking, the way of knowing the complex connections of nature, things, society, and the transmission of this information through communication.

First, let's figure out what speech errors are. Speech errors are any cases of deviation from the current language norms. Without their knowledge, a person can live normally, work and set up communication with others. But the effectiveness of the actions performed in certain cases may suffer. In this regard, there is a risk of being misunderstood. And in situations where our personal success depends on it, this is unacceptable.

Classification of speech errors. Speech errors can be classified according to the units of processing and types of mechanism involved. The units involved in slips of the tongue range from phrases, words saying

“pass the pepper” instead of “pass the salt”,

morphemes, phonemes saying

“flock of 2 bats” instead of “block of flats”,

to features saying

“turn the knop” instead of “knob.

Mechanisms include anticipations saying

“the first of May” instead of “the first

Perseverations saying

“God rest re merry gentleman” instead of “God rest ye”,

Exchanges

“Guess whose mind came to name?” instead of “name came to mind”),
substitutions (“Get me a fork” instead of knife),

and blends saying “chung” for “children” and “young”.

Two particular types of speech error deserve special mention.

Spoonerisms are errors where the initial consonants of words have exchanged. They are named after the Reverend Dr William Archibald Spooner, Warden of New College, Oxford, who was particularly prone to making this type of error and indeed, who may have suffered from a developmental language disorder. Some examples of alleged errors made by Dr Spooner are:

. You have wasted the whole term -> You have tasted the whole worm.

The Lord is a loving shepherd to his flock -> The Lord is a shoving leopard to his flock. Note that in both of these examples the error strings produced form words; these errors are therefore possible instances of the lexical bias effect described below. Malapropisms are named after Mrs Malaprop, a character in Sheridan’s play “The Rivals”. Mrs Malaprop often used grand words incorrectly, such as saying “epitaphs” for 3 “epithets” and “reprehend” for “apprehend”. Following Fay and Cutler, the term has been used for all phonological word substitutions that inadvertently arise from processing difficulty, rather than ignorance, such as:

Liszt’s Hungarian rhapsody -> Liszt’s Hungarian restaurant.

Interpretation of speech errors - speech production comprises conceptualization, formulation, and encoding. [1, P.47] Conceptualization involves determining what to say – we form the message. Formulation involves translating the message into a linguistic form, and has two aspects: syntactic planning and lexicalisation (the process whereby word concepts are turned into sounds). Finally, execution involves detailed phonetic and articulatory planning.

Speech errors have informed our understanding of all of these stages. It is important to note that the occurrence of slips of the tongue is not random. In particular, some sorts of errors that could occur do not

we do not observe function words exchanging with content words.

This order is the basis for explaining how and why errors arise in terms of a model of speech production. The basic idea is that for an error to occur, the two elements of the error or intended and actual outcome must be simultaneously active at the same level of processing. For example, words exchange with words, but content words only exchange with other content words, and function words with other function words; content words do not exchange with function words, or vice versa. This finding is extraordinarily robust: in my corpus of several thousand speech errors, there is not a single instance of a content word exchanging with a function word.

Syntactic planning - the extension of this type of argument led to the development of the standard, or the Fromkin-Garrett, model of speech production. Consider the following famous example from Fromkin.

a weekend for MANIACs -> a maniac for WEEKENDs

The capital letters indicate the primary sentence stress and the italics secondary stress. The error left the stress unchanged, suggesting that stress is generated independently of the particular words involved. Note also that the plural morpheme “-s” remained where it was originally intended to be: it did not move with “maniac”, but instead was stranded.

The phonological representations of content words are then accessed from the lexicon using the semantic representation. Content words are then inserted into the syntactic planning frame where final positions are specified to form the positional level. The function words and other grammatical elements are then phonologically specified to give the sound-level representation. Sound exchanges occur at this stage and, as their absolute position is now specified, such errors are constrained by distance. Garrett’s model accounts for a great deal of the speech error evidence, but a number of subsequent observations suggested that some aspects of it might not be correct. First, it is not at all clear that speech production is strictly serial. There is

clearly some evidence for at least local parallel processing in word blend errors, which must be explained by two or more words being simultaneously retrieved from the lexicon, as in. More problematically, we find blends of phrases and sentences. Furthermore, the locus of these blends is determined phonologically, so that the two phrases cross over where they are most similar in sound, suggesting that the alternative messages are processed in parallel from the message to the sound levels.⁶ We also observe cognitive intrusion errors where material extraneous to the utterance intrudes into it. The message level can intrude into lower levels of processing, producing non-plan-internal errors. These errors are often phonologically facilitated, meaning that errors are more likely to occur if the target word and intrusion sound alike. [2, 73-108pp] The names of objects or words in the outside environment can also intrude into speech, producing environmental contamination errors. Once again we find that phonological facilitation of environmental contaminants occurs more often than one would expect by chance (although to a lesser degree than with other cognitive intrusions). 5. Utterance:

It's difficult to valify. (Targets: validate + verify)

Utterance:

I'm making the kettle on. (Target 1: I'm making some tea. + Target 2: I'm putting the kettle on.)

Utterance:

I've eaten all my library books. (Target: I've read all my library books. Context: The speaker reported that he was hungry and was thinking of getting something to eat.) .

Utterance:

Get out of the clark. (Target: Get out of the car. Context: The speaker was looking at a shop-front in the background that had the name “Clark’s” printed on it; he was not aware of this when he spoke.)

Lexical access. - there is a consensus that lexicalization is a two-stage process. When we produce a word, processing moves from the semantic level to an

intermediate level containing lemmas, which are specified syntactically and semantically. Although the idea that lexicalisation occurs in two stages appears to be supported by evidence from other sources such as picture naming, tip-of-the-tongue states, studies of people with anomia, and brain imaging, there is nevertheless some dissent. [3,505-520pp]

Natural speech is full of mismatches between intention and output. Slips of the tongue are errors involving the sounds or words of the language, and provide a window onto the processes of speech production. Errors can be classified according to the units of speech and the mechanisms involved. Analysis of speech errors shows that production occurs takes place in stages, with content words and function words being accessed at different stages, with some interaction between levels of processing.

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